

Ligand Replacement in Metal Acetylacetonates by Ethylenediaminetetra Acetic Acid*

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Though question has been raised¹ as to the ability of an EDTA anion to occupy six coordination positions in the coordination sphere, a number of types of evidences for its hexadentate nature have been cited^{2,3}. Solid EDTA chelates of metals have been prepared in many instances using simple metal salts and alkali or ammonium salts of EDTA⁴⁻⁸. Possibilities of anion penetration⁹ leaves in doubt the exact composition of the products obtained. It was, therefore, of interest to synthesize metal-EDTA chelates by ligand replacement.

Several metal acetylacetonates, for instance, copper(II), nickel(II), cerium(III), lanthanum(III), neodymium (III), zirconium(IV) and thorium (IV) were found in this investigation to react with EDTA in aqueous suspension. From the resulting solutions, well-defined crystals of metal-EDTA chelates have been obtained. When equivalent quantities are used the reaction proceeds to completion. The solution so obtained does not contain any other crystallizable substance, nor anions which can penetrate, so that almost theoretical yield of the pure substance is possible.

The best use of this method, however, has been in the preparation of manganese (III) chelate of EDTA. A very well defined and stable non-ionic compound showing the unusual oxidation state of three for manganese is its acetylacetonate¹⁰. This has been used for the preparation of the EDTA chelate. However, the corresponding acid ($\text{MnHY} \cdot n\text{H}_2\text{O}$) was found to decompose on standing in solution. Hence the stable potassium salt ($\text{KMnY} \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$) was prepared using the acetylacetonate, EDTA and potassium hydroxide in the right proportion. EDTA chelate of titanium(IV) was also prepared. However, in this preparation the starting material used was dichlorobis(acetylacetonato) titanium(IV) and hence the disodium salt of EDTA was employed in place of EDTA. Due to the presence of sodium chloride in solution, only a small first crop was obtained pure ($\text{TiY} \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$).

* NCL Communication No. 1114.

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Infrared spectra of the compounds have been found to be similar to those reported^{4,6,7,9,11}.

EXPERIMENTAL

KMn.Y.2H₂O: Powdered manganese (III) acetylacetonate (3.52 g.; 0.01 mole) was added to a thoroughly stirred mixture of potassium hydroxide (0.56 g.; 0.01 mole) and EDTA (3.73 g.; 0.01 mole) in cold water (15 ml.). A deep red solution was obtained, which was filtered. Cold alcohol (20 ml.) was added and the mixture kept in a refrigerator for 2 days. Well-defined deep red crystals were obtained. Another crop was obtained by adding more alcohol (10 ml.), and cooling again. Washed with alcohol and sucked dry. Yield: 2.5 g. (60%). Found: C, 28.93; H, 3.61; N, 6.75; Mn, 13.26%. $C_{10}H_{16}N_2O_{10}KMn$ requires: C, 28.71; H, 3.83; N, 6.70, Mn, 13.14%.

TiY.H₂O: Powdered dichloro-bis(acetylacetonato) titanium(IV) complex (3.17 g.; 0.01 mole) was added to a solution of disodium salt of EDTA (3.72 g.; 0.01 mole) in water (100 ml.). After stirring briskly, it was filtered. To the clear filtrate alcohol was added with stirring until turbidity appeared. At this stage it was allowed to crystallize slowly. Uniform white crystals. Washed with alcohol and sucked dry. Yield: 1.2 g. (35%). Another crop obtained was found to be contaminated. Found: C, 33.98; H, 4.21; N, 8.05; Ti, 13.81%. Required for $C_{10}H_{14}N_2O_9Ti$: C, 33.90; H, 3.96; N, 7.91; Ti, 13.53%.

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Received September 9, 1963.

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